

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B258
Date: 16 January 2007
Take Off 09:59:18Z 16:13:05Z
Landing: 14:58:02Z 16:57:37Z
Flight Time 4h58m44 0h44m30

Campaign: WINTEX – CAESAR

Operating Area: N Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Ben Johnson	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	AVAPS	Stuart Heath	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	ARIES	Stuart Newman	Met Office
9	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
10	MARSS & DEIMOS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
11	Mission Scientist 2	Phil Brown	Met Office
12			
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Flight Track:

B258 Track 16-JAN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b258
 Date: 16 Jan 2007
 Project: WINTEX - CAESAR
 Location: North Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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085809		Start-Up	0.34 kft	126	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
093301		INU	0.34 kft	126	To Navigate mode
095918		T/O	0.97 kft	215	Cranfield
100500		Turb Probe	24.0 kft	300	P0 Frozen
102620		Video	18.0 kft	327	Start FFC & UFC/DFC
105402	105627	Profile 1	24.0 - 26.0 kft	093	
105928	110130	Profile 1	26.0 - 28.0 kft	252	
110131	111544	Run 1	28.0 kft	256	
110340		Heimann	28.0 kft	260	Cal +5 to -2C
111706	112011	Profile 2	28.0 - 26.1 kft	347	
112011	112531	Run 2	26.1 - 26.0 kft	352	
112800	113253	Profile 3.1	26.0 - 21.6 kft	184	Sawtooth 1
113254	113930	Profile 3.2	21.5 - 28.0 kft	190	
114112	115006	Profile 4.1	28.0 - 20.1 kft	117	Sawtooth 2
115007	115510	Profile 4.2	20.1 - 24.5 kft	118	
115510	120813	Run 3	24.5 kft	138	In Cirrus
115758		Video	24.5 kft	139	Change Tapes
120954	121630	Profile 5	24.6 - 30.0 kft	331	500fpm
121828	122043	Profile 6	30.0 - 28.0 kft	327	
122248	123314	Run 4	28.1 kft	163	
123314	123553	Profile 7	28.1 - 30.0 kft	181	
123752	124930	Run 5	30.0 kft	347	Contrailling
123815		Sonde	30.1 kft	354	Launch #01
124324		Sonde	30.0 kft	325	Launch #02
124853		Sonde	30.0 kft	325	Launch #03
125129	125958	Profile 8	30.0 - 22.0 kft	165	
130023	130315	Profile 9	22.0 - 24.0 kft	177	
130620	131722	Run 6	24.0 kft	346	
131924	132516	Profile 10.1	24.0 - 30.0 kft	165	Sawtooth 3
132517	133016	Profile 10.2	30.0 - 26.0 kft	178	
133220	134416	Run 7	26.0 kft	345	
133609		Video	26.0 kft	329	Change Tapes
134417	134642	Profile 11	26.0 - 28.0 kft	329	
134917	135115	Profile 11	28.0 - 30.0 kft	168	
135203	135921	Run	30.0 kft	171	
135921	140652	Profile 12	29.6 - 22.0 kft	178	
140847	141128	Profile 12	22.0 - 20.0 kft	347	
141128	142131	Run 9	20.0 kft	329	
141358		Heimann	20.0 kft	331	Cal - suspect
145802		Land	0.30 kft	245	Newcastle - Refuel
155809		Position	0.31 kft	197	55'02.00N, 1'41.93W
161305		T/O	0.99 kft	245	Newcastle
162510		Event	13.0 kft	148	Deimos ON (CO Test)
164533		Event	8.2 kft	192	Deimos OFF
165737		Land	0.41 kft	260	Cranfield
170151		Shutdown	0.40 kft	312	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B258 Track 16-JAN-07

CAESAR Sortie Brief

Radar validation and intercomparison of cirrus microphysics

B258 16/1/07

Aim:

The aim of this sortie is to obtain a good statistical representation of the in-situ microphysics of a frontal or convective cirrus case, which is coincident with radar measurements from CloudSat. Measurements should be made between fixed ground points (not advecting with the wind), so that the cirrus is well represented. The exact location and duration of the runs are to be determined from the cirrus location.

A few runs above and below the cloud are to be made for radiative measurements, in addition to the saw tooth manoeuvres for the in-situ measurements.

Coincident with CloudSat overpass 12:45

CLLOUDSAT 2007/01/16 UTC CLOUDSAT ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT EPOCH DATE: 07/01/03
■ lat: 51.57 lon: 358.69 res: 9 km

Weather conditions:

Convective, frontal or Lee wave cirrus, ideally with clear skies below. It is essential to be able to get above the cirrus. Small amounts of low cloud are acceptable if they are measurable by the radar.

Locations:

Over sea (under or slightly upwind of the CloudSat sub-orbital track).

Clearances:

NOTAMS will be required for dropping sondes.

Instruments required:

Critical: SID1, 2DC, 2DP, FFSSP, Temp, Humidity

Desirable: SID2, CIPs, CPI, AVAPS, ARIES, SWS, MARSS, TAFTS, SHIMS, Heimann,

Core chem (automatic mode acceptable)

Sub-orbital satellite points:

A) 53.859 N, 3.3728 E (decimal points)

B) 57.3816 N, 1.4937 E

Fly along section of sub-orbital track where the cirrus is located.

The footprint of the CloudSat radar is 1.4km (across track) x 2.5km (along track).

B258 16/1/07**CAESAR radar validation**

		Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1		Takeoff from Cranfield		
2	1000	Transit to cirrus location under or slightly upwind of the suborbital track, to a level 1000ft below the cloud base.	70	70
3	1110	Perform a series of ascending and descending profiles in a saw tooth pattern through the cirrus to an altitude of 1000ft above and below the cloud respectively, along or perpendicular to the wind, covering fixed ground positions A - B.	80	150
5	1230	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus	10	160
6	1240	1 straight and level run above cloud, of 10 mins. Drop 1 or 2 sondes. Satellite overpass ideally during run.	10	170
7	1250	Reciprocal straight and level run above cloud, of 10 mins.	10	180
8	1300	Perform a series of ascending and descending profiles in a saw tooth pattern through the cirrus to an altitude of 1000ft above and below the cloud respectively, between A and B	80	260
9	1420	Profile descent to 1000ft below cirrus	10	270
9	1430	1 straight and level run 1000ft below cirrus base, of 10 mins	10	280
11	1440	Transit to Newcastle for refuel	30	310
12	1510	Land		

Note: additional time has been given for the outbound transit to ensure the best cirrus section has been identified along the sub-orbital track.

If cirrus is not extending to subsatellite area then change to:

Option 2: Radiative properties of cirrus

Aim:

The aim of this sortie is to determine the radiative properties of frontal cirrus using multiple frequencies from the range of remote sensing instruments on the aircraft. For closure it is also important to determine the in-situ properties of the cloud and to make radiative measurements of the atmosphere above and below the cirrus. To obtain in-situ vertical distributions either perform profile ascents and descents, or a Lagrangian spiral descent if the cirrus is extensive and homogenous. Measurements should be made **advecting with the wind**, such that the same airmass is continuously measured.

Straight and level runs should be made below, above and in the cirrus. A 100ft run over the sea will be required to measure the SST. Orbits are to be made below the cloud with SWS viewing upwards to determine the phase function of the ice particles.

Coincident with AQUA overpass at 12:44

Weather conditions:

Convective, frontal or Lee wave cirrus. Clear sky below the cirrus in the measurement area is essential. Ideally the cirrus should not extend above 35,000ft.

Locations:

North sea.

Clearances:

NOTAMS will be required for dropping sondes and runs at 100ft.

Instruments required:

Critical: ARIES, SWS, SID1, 2DC, Temp, Humidity, AVAPS

Desirable: MARSS, TAFTS, SHIMS, CPI, SID2, FFSSP, 2DP, CIPs, Heimann, Core chem (auto mode OK)

	Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	Takeoff from Cranfield		0
2	Transit at appropriate level to enter operating area at min altitude	45	45
3	Straight and level run of 10 mins duration at 100 ft over sea only.	10	55
4	Profile ascent from min altitude to 1000ft below cirrus base at 1000ft/min (interrupted when necessary)	35	90
5	Fly 3 straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft below cirrus, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins.	35	125
6	Fly two orbits below cloud at SZA (or max) banking angle	10	135
7	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus base	5	140
8	Fly one straight and level run in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	150
9	Profile ascent to 1000ft below cirrus top	10	160
10	Fly one straight and level run in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	170
11	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus top	5	175
12	Fly three straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft above cirrus, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins. Drop between 1 and 3 sondes during one run, ideally during satellite overpass	35	210
13	EITHER Perform a Lagrangian spiral descent at 2 ms-1, advecting with the wind, to 1000ft below cirrus base, then go to 16	25	235
13	OR Profile descent to level approx. half way between cloud top and base	5	215
14	Fly 1 or 2 straight and level runs 1000ft in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	225
15	Profile descent to 1000ft below cloud base	10	235
16	Fly one straight and level run 1000ft below cirrus base, orientated across wind, of 10 mins.	10	245
17	Perform one orbit at SZA (or max) banking angle	5	250
18	Profile descent to transit altitude	10	260
19	Transit to Newcastle for refuel or directly to Cranfield	45	305

Additional activities:

Observation of contrail presence or absence behind aircraft.

The aim is to acquire data that can be used to provide additional validation of a new contrail prediction algorithm that is being developed for defence customer use.

Weather conditions: No special conditions required but contrail formation is unlikely at temperatures warmer than about -45 degC.

Manoeuvres: No special manoeuvres required.

Special instrument instructions: When operating below -45 degC, the video-recording should be switched to include the rear-facing camera, unless otherwise required by the main mission science. Mission scientist 2 should monitor the video display and record log entries for both presence *and absence* of contrails behind the aircraft.

Instrument operator instructions:

ARIES and SWS

- Both instruments must point in the same direction as each other (except during cal). ARIES needs to tell SWS where it is pointing.
- Majority of time should be towards the cloud (or sea at 100ft)
- However, still need some data pointing away to characterise the atmosphere above and below the cloud (e.g. ~2 mins of 10 min run)
- For orbits both instruments should view towards cloud for whole time

ARIES

- Be careful when viewing zenith that the instrument remains stable. 1 min views with 1 min calcs seem to be OK.
- let SWS know which viewing direction and when.

SWS

- Zenith = 6 deg forward

Ben Johnson

16 Jan 2007

CAESAR cirrus flight

Weather:

Cirrus associated with a warm / occluded frontal system over the central north sea and a separate patch of cirrus (not associated with large-scale fronts) off the coast of Scotland and moving rapidly west during the day.

Operating region:

North Sea off the coast of S. Scotland and N. England out to the track of the Aqua overpass.

Mission objectives:

In-situ and radiation measurements of cirrus coincident with an Aqua cloudsat overpass.

Flight patterns:

Take off from Cranfield. Transit to Teeside at mid-levels. Cirrus thickening during transit but clearing on arriving in operating region. Initially a considerable amount of time was spent trying to locate some good areas of cirrus to work in. Cloud was patchy, thin in the vertical and in layers at different altitudes. Got some good profiles and runs in clouds going up the coast of Scotland to Aberdeen, then turned south again and then out west towards the satellite track to start a series of stacked SLR patterns coincident in space and time with the cloudsat overpass. Picked up some cirrus on the way out to the track. Generally tops were around 30,000ft and it was difficult to get above the cloud until later in the flight. Some SLRs were made at 31,000ft just above the cloud top, or occasionally skimming the cloud top. Runs were also performed below the cloud at 20,000ft followed by a series of orbits at that altitude before heading to Newcastle for a refuel and return to Cranfield.

Summary:

A good flight for sawtooth and SLR sampling through cirrus, some useful radiation measurements above the cirrus. Cirrus was patchy in the horizontal and at various altitudes between 20,000 and 30,000ft.

Mission Scientist's Log

20 mins
100 mins
30 mins
360 km/hr

Flight No **B. 258** Date **16/1/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
100001					T10
101200		FL130			Transit at FL130
102500		FL260			Climb to continue transit
103200		FL240		54.5 1E	Encountered cloud base ~ FL215
		Tephigram shows moist from FL200 upwards			
		Some higher v. thin layers of c. above			
	P1	FL240	E	56N, 1.3W	Climb because patch of
105657	Intercept	FL260	E	56, 0.3E	Cirrus is ^{is} above us. missed it
105928	Continue P1	FL260	W		Clear skies below apart from
110131	End P1	FL280	E		5% small scraps of marine Sc
110131	Start P1	FL280	245		Cirrus to the W and NW
110300	"	"	260		turning towards ^{more} northerly to aim
111556	End P1		"		for the cirrus
111534	P2				
111534	P2	FL280	260		missed cloud again
112011	R2	FL260	0		cloud encountered on
112531	P2	"	0		northerly run close to coast
112800	P3.1	FL260	190		cloud encountered during
113254	P3.2	FL215	190		P3.1 & P.32, running back south
113930	End P3.2	FL280	190		
114112	P4.1	FL280	120	56N 1W	NO cloud here heading out
11	End P4.1	FL200	120		east to the
	P4.2	FL245	100		Satellite track.
115510	R3	FL245	140		Approaching cloud
120000	"	FL245	110	55N	went through some cirrus

cloud

Mission Scientist's Log

SGN

Flight No **B.258** Date **16/1/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **2** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
120813	End R3	FL245	E		Variable cloud amounts, going in and out of it
121828					Reaching satellite track (A)
121923					
120954	P5	FL245	N	A	Going along satellite track cloud tops around FL290
121630	End P5	FL300	N	B	
121828	P6	FL300	N		A = Southern tip of satellite track at SGN
	End P6	FL280	N		
122248	P4	FL280	S		B = Northern tip of satellite track at SGN
123314	End R4	FL280	S		
123314	P7	FL280	S		Still variable patches of cloud
123553	End P7	FL300	S		Some wisps of cloud at FL300 but not much
123752	R5	FL300	N		
123815	"	"	N		Sonde 1 gone
124324	"	"	N		Sonde 2 gone
124853	"	"	N		Sonde 3 gone
12453	End R5	"	N		Sondes dropped beginning, middle and end of track.
125129	P8	FL300	S		Saw tooth 300-220-240
125958	End P8	FL220	S		
130023	P9	FL220	S		still inter
130315	End P9	FL240	S		Run @ FL220 - intermittent cloud amounts
130620	R6	FL240	N		Run @ FL240
131924	P10	FL240	S		Saw tooth 240 ³⁰⁰ -260
132516	P10.2	FL300	S		
133016		FL260	S		
133220	R7	FL260	N		Run @ FL260

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.258** Date **16/1/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **3** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134416	End R7	FL260	N		Run at FL260 was also
134417	P11.1	FL260	N		intermittently through cloud
134642	End P11.2	FL280	N		Cloud still patchy & intermittent and at all levels
135150	End P12	FL300			
135150	R8	FL300			
134917	P11.2	FL300	S		Run above cloud for radiative work
135150	R8	FL300	S		
135950	End R8	FL300	S		
	P12	FL300	S		Descent Descent to FL200
140652	Interrupt	FL220	S		cloud base at FL200
140847	Resume P12	FL220	N		run below cloud for radiative work
141158	End P12	FL200	N		
141158	R9	FL200	N	FL 300	Still in cloud at southern extreme
142131	End R9	FL200	N		
142131	END OF SCIENCE				
					Scrapped idea of orbits because cloud too inhomogeneous.

55 N 2.6 E

~~55~~

56 2.3 E

Mission Scientist's Log #2Flight No **B.258** Date 16/1/07 Name Phil Brown Page 1 of 5
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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
095851					T/O roll. Heavy rain.
1015		13000	348		On track over Lides. in thick cloud of frontal zone
1020					P has series of sawtooth oscillations.
1033					P sawtooth continues.
1057					Pa also frozen at about same time.
1058					Turning down dimb. Nice convulus in semi-streets cut over N sea to the SE and E.
111624		28000			Have just run towards W, turning N to run N up 2°W meridian.
					Seems to be quite dense Ci band below top of Ci, Sfc obscured so its quite dense.
1119		27000			
112011		26000	350	56 18.0 -1 54.0	End P2 / Start R2
1124		"			Cleared N extent of that piece of Ci.
112530		"			End R2 & descend.
113254		21500			End P3.1 / Start P3.2
115145		21300			In profile 4.2
					Turning slightly more to SE to intercept thicker patch.
			138		3/8 shallow Ci on LWS of track.
115510		24500	138		End P4.2 / Start R3
1200	3				Continging SE to reach start point of satellite track.
120813	3				End run.
120954	P5	25000			to FL 300

Mission Scientist's Log #2

Flight No **B.258** Date 16/1/07 Name Phil Brown Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121435		28500			In profile, cloud currently thin but looks thicker out to SW in the into-wind direction.
121828		30000			PG to F-280.
122043		28000			End PG & start R4
122245		28000	161		Start R4 parallel to last track.
1225					Low particle cones here.
1233					approaching end of run, cloud was clearly patchy, ocean regions where sp. obscure.
123314		28000	181		End R4 / P7 for 300 next run is overpass & sondes.
123752		30000	352		R5
			336		SIDI ~ 10/sec just in top of cloud layer.
			326		End run, turn & profile to 220
125129		-11	164		Start P8
		27500			Top of a layer here & can see clearly the wisps we had earlier.
		22500			end P8
		24000			at P9 & turn N for run.
130545		"			Nice rosettes. SIDI ~ 100
130620		"	347		Start R6
					More blobular at start.
					-40°C so all good for SIDI 2 dex.
1311		"			SIDI ~ 100, blobules & rosettes.

Mission Scientist's Log # 2

Flight No **B.258** Date 16/1/07 Name P. Brown Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
131924		24000	163	55 42.0 +2 12.0	Start P10.1 to Fl 300 then 260
/		28000			again getting mostly above again.
/		28300			humidity rises as descend back into layer
133016		26000			end P10.2
133220		26000			Start R7 Nbound.
1339		"			22° halo visible.
133943					no v. bright.
		30000			End R8 / start probe.
140652		22000			P12 intercept. cloud at this level. maybe slopes upward toward the N. Turn back N.
/					Seem to be in the lower band assoc with frontal wave.
141141					
142133		20000			End run / end science.
					Just coming under edge of Ci band at N end of run.
/				55 48.0 2 18.0	
1442					Run confis was maybe like this at end
					Going W to Newcastle cloud is further to S.

Mission Scientist's Log

#2

Flight No **B.258** Date Name Page **4** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1446					During recovery, P_a rising to 115 hPa, well outside its normal operating range. What is spec. of the transducer.
145853					Just at end of landing roll, P_a seems to have unfrozen just at end of approach, P_o remains frozen.
—					<p>lifted the radome. Seemed to be water on the outside of some of the pipes but nothing obvious on the inside. Lowered the radome, saw droplet of water within the lower attack port. Opened water trap but nothing.</p> <p>C_a - check, - OK throughout. This is differential between top & centre.</p> <p>Deduce that P_o must be blocked somewhere close to the sensor.</p> <p>Similarly, maybe lower side of P_a is also blocked close to the sensor.</p>
1557					<p>Just prior to 40. P_o still giving false reading. All others OK.</p> <p>Or maybe P_a is blocked on the upper side, between the sensor and the connection to check sensor</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B258 **T/O:** 095918
Date of flight: 16/1/07 **Land:** 145802

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	N N N	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	N N	File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown (see comment box) e) End time: 240000 if unknown	N N N N N	Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	N N N N N N N N	Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit	N N N	Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	N N N N	Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? In flight_plot, parameters JW LWC para 535 Nevzorov LWC para 602 FFSSP LWC para 1202 ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.	N N N N N N	Synchronized? Not done

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B258
Date of Flight: 16/1/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer B258.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (B258.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS	Y	
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B258.zip	Y	Size of B245.dat =797056
6) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	Y	Blocks read =114703
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B258.dat	Y	Blocks written = 114703
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B258_seadas.dat	Y	Bad reads =0
WAVE> exit	Y	
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	Y	
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	Y	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B258_seadas.dat	Y	
d) Comment string:	Y	
e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i>	Y	Start = 095500
f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i>	Y	End = 150000
g) Read 2DC: Y	Y	Ignore error message scroll
h) Read 2DP: Y	Y	(vestigial error from tapes)
i) Secondary data: Y	Y	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	Y	Are FRW, FSP, IMB,
k) cmd.str: Y	Y	PCA,SEC
l) Auto time correction: N	Y	files in PMSDATA?
m) Full length secondary: N	y	Are they non-zero in size? yes
8) FLOODS> WAVE		2D image display and printing
i). WAVE> imagedisplay		Must be done from FLOODS itself.
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: B258		
c) Time from IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i>		
f) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i>		
g) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images)		Note any problems with images
ii). WAVE> auto_image		Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: B258		
c) Enter date: 20070116		
d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i>		Start = 095800
e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i>		End =145700
f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10		
iii). WAVE> exit to create files		FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_
iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps
v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		Notes on this in instructions
vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B258_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =b</p> <p>Start =0 End = 240000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 121006 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat yes</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =31</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X =b Y = (X+1) c</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>		<p>Correlated? Not done</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B258
Date of Flight: 16/1/2007

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	Y	
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	Y	
a) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	Y	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP	Y	
Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary)	Y	
PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	Y	
d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i>	Y	Min size =1
<i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i>	Y	
	Y	
e) Calibration volume flow rate:	Y	Vol flow rate = 1.8
<i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i>	Y	
<i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i>	Y	
<i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i>	Y	
f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i>	Y	
g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i>	Y	
h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	
3) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	Y	
ii). WAVE> exit	Y	
4) FLOODS> MODIFY	Y	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	Y	
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	Y	X =a
c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY	Y	Y = X+1 =b
d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	
5) CHECKS		
Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		Merged OK?

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 258** Date **16/01/07** Operat or(s) **AW** log page **1** of **2**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

093000						PREFLIGHT OK			
093000						DARK ALL			
100000						take off error field.			
100417	—	Climb out	174°A	400		Scene all in transit. USH 300 LSH 750			
104711		240	6° F			SWS to ZENITH			
105402	P1	240 →	6° F	400		Start P1 → FL280			
105627	P1	260	6° F	400		INT P1 @ FL260			
105928	P1	"	"	"		Restart P1			
110131	P1/R1	280	6° F	400		and P1/start R1. INT TIMES USH 300 LSH 750			
110525				750		SWS to 750, USH 300 & LSH 1000 + DARK ALL			
110550		280	6° F	750		Scene all.			
110710						LSH to 500 & DARK			
110720						LSH Scene.			
110930			174°A			SWS to NADIR.			
111410		280	174° A	400		SWS to 400ms + DARK			
111420						SWS scene.			
111544	R1		174°A	400		end R1			
111706	P2					Start P2 → FL260			
112011	P2/R2	260	174°A	400		end P2/start R2			
112531	R2	260	174°A	400		end R2			
112800	P3.1	260 ↓	174°A	400		Start P3.1 Sawtooth			
113253	P3.1/P3.2	215 →				end P3.1 start P3.2			
113930	P3.2/P3.3	280 ↓							
113952	P3.3	280				end P3.3			
114112	P4.1	280 ↓	174°A	400		Start P4.1.			
114400						DARK ALL			
114424				400		Scene all INT TIMES USH 300 LSH 500			
115007	P4.1/P4.2	FL200	174°A	400		end P4.1/P4.2			
115200			6° F	400		SWS to Zenith.			
115249			6° F	750		SWS to 750ms, USH 300, LSH 750 + DARK ALL			
115308						Scene all			
115510	P4.2/R3	245	6° F	750		and P4.2 start R3.			
115657				400		SWS to 400ms + DARK			
115703		245	6° F	400		SWS scene			
120755						LSH to 400 + DARK			
120808						LSH Scene			
120813	R3	245				end R3			
120954	P5					Start P5 → FL300			
121030	P5	300	6° F	400		and P5 @ FL300.			
121828	P6		6 → 74° F	400		Start P6			
122135			174°A	400		SWS to NADIR			
122143	P6					end P6			
122245	R4	280	174°A	400		Start R4			
122630						DARK ALL			
122642						Scene all.			
123314	R4/P7	280 →	174°A	400		and R4/start P7			
123553	P7	300				end P7			
123630		300	174°A	250		SWS + LSH to 250ms + DARK ALL			
123647		300	174°A			Scene all			
123752	R5					Start R5			
124930	R5					end R5			
125129	P8	300 ↓	174°A	250		Start P8			
125058	P8	220				end P8			

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 258** Date **16/1/07** Operat or(s) **Av** log page **2** of **2**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
130023	P9	220	174°A	250		Start P9			
130315	P9	240	---	---		end P9			
130620	R6	240	174°A	250		Start R6			
130720						DARK ALL			
130740			174°A	250		Scene all INT. USH 300 LSH 250			
131722	R6	240	174°A	250		end R6			
131924	P10.1	240 →	174°A			Start P10.1 to FL300.			
						Broken Sc below & thin ci above.			
132517	P10.1/P10.2	300 ↘	174°A	250		end P10.1 start P10.2			
133016	P10.2	260							
133220	R7	260	174°A	250		Start R7			
133850				400		SWS + LSH to 400ms + DARK ALL			
133915	R7	260	174°A	400		Scene all			
						over broken Sc below. Clear above.			
134417	R7/P11	260 →	174°A	400		end R7 start P11 → R280			
134642	P11	280				int P11			
134917		280 →				Restart P11 to FL300			
135115	P11/R8	300	174°A	400		end P11 start R8 above ci			
135216				500		SWS to 500ms, LSH to 750ms DARK ALL			
135227	R8	300	174°A	500		Scene all. NADIR SWS VIEW			
135505			174°A	500		LSH to 500ms + DARK			
5515		300	---	500		LSH Scene.			
						Nice LSH & SWS NADIR SIGNAL.			
135921	R8/P12	300 ↘							
140258	P12	250	6°F	500		in cloud (ci). SWS to Zenith for next run.			
140652	P12	220				int P12			
140744						DARK all			
140758						Scene all			
140847	P12	220	6°F	500		restart P12 → FL200			
141128	P12/R9	200	6°F	500		end P12 & start R9			
141608						LSH to 1000ms + DARK			
141633			6°F	500		LSH to Scene.			
141707						USH to 500ms + DARK			
141717						USH Scene			
142131	R9	200	6°F	500		end R9 & END OF SCIENCE			
142408						DATA STOP			

ARIES flight log

Flight: B258

page 1 of 3

Date: 16/1/07

Operator(s): S. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CAESAR RADAR VALIDATION FLIGHT, NORTH SEA

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
093035		1x60	C	C	71.0	31.0	GROUND TESTS
093110		1x60	H	C	71.1	30.8	
093145		120x1	N ⁵	C	71.0	31.0	(the pan) ! N-5° by mistake
093256		120x1	Z	O	70.9	31.0	overcast and raining
093409		1x60	C	⊙	71.0	31.4	
093443		1x60	H	⊙	70.9	30.9	
<hr/>							
095922		TAKE-OFF					
103853	FL ²⁴⁰ 280	1x60	C	C	71.0	31.0	In transit, clear slot
103930		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.2	
104007		120x1	N	C	70.7	29.9	Looks clear below
104116		120x1	Z	O	70.1	30.3	Clear or v. thin above (sub-vis. if any)
104223		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.6	
104300		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.7	
105609	FL260	1x30	C	C			in climb, interruption
105633		1x30	H	C			
105700		120x1	Z	O	70.3	30.8	(includes turn) to s'board looks clear above
105804		1x30	C	⊙!			
105823		1x30	H	⊙!			
105907	FL ²⁶⁰ -270?	120x1	N	C	70.5	30.7	105935 climb to FL280
110010		1x30	C	C			
110028		1x30	H	C			
110302	R1	1x60	C	C	70.6	71.2	
110335	FL280	1x60	H	C	70.6	30.3	
110411		120x1	N	C	70.6	31.0	Hazy below but can see the ocean - possibly v. thin cloud?
110516		1x60	C	C	70.7	30.3	
110555		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.0	
110658		120x1	Z	O	69.7	30.8	Clear above
110805		120x1	N	C	71.0	30.6	Just getting into cloud? At times.
110923		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.6	
110956		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.5	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B258

page 2 of 3

Date: 16/1/07 Operator(s): S. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NORTH SEA CAESAR FLIGHT

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11 4602	(sawtooth)	1x60	C	C	70.5	30.4	NB. not sure if data are viable in sawtooth
11 4640	"	1x60	H	C	70.6	30.8	
11 4721	"	120x1	Z	0	70.4	30.2	looks clear above + below
11 4835	"	120x1	N	C	70.1	30.6	Unobstructed view of sea surface
11 4941	"	1x60	C	C	70.5	30.7	
11 5027	"	1x60	H	C	70.7	30.5	(Descent into & ascent)
122000	P66	1x60	C	C	70.7	30.6	Too early, still in profile
122245	FL280 R4	1x60	C	C	70.6	30.8	
122338		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.2	
122427		300x1	N	C	70.6	30.4	Close to tops or in thin thin cloud? Cloud visible just below + Cu further below
122702		1x60	C	C	70.6	29.8	1226 turning manoeuvre
122746		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.6	
123255	FL300 R5	1x60	C	C	70.3	30.4	
123828		1x60	H	C	70.3	30.7	
123909		300x1	N	C	70.7	31.0	thin-ish cloud directly below, CuSc further below
124155		1x60	C	C	70.3	30.7	
124231		1x60	H	C	70.7	30.3	
124325		480x1	N	C	69.3	29.9	v. thin Ci below, mid-level Cu clearly visible thicker 1246, thin again 1247
124744		1x60	C	C	60.7	29.8	
124820		1x60	H	C	60.7	30.6	
135125	R8 FL300	1x60	C	C	60.8	30.6	
135158		1x60	H	C	60.6	30.6	
135236		480x1	N	C	60.7	29.9	Extensive CuSc field below, v. thin Ci barely visible; thicker though still partially transparent at 1354
135639		1x60	C	C	60.6	30.2	
135716		1x60	H	C	60.9	31.3	
135754		120x1	N	C	60.7	29.9	thicker (lower?) below clear above
135903		1x60	C	C	60.1	30.0	
135936		1x60	H	C	60.9	30.3	In profile descent
		140210	DRS = ARIES EXACTLY				
141139	R9	1x60	C	C	60.8	30.9	
141214		1x60	H	C	60.5		

61.0 30.5

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	16/01/07	Flight	B258	log pages
Operator(s)	Jeff Brown		Campaign	WINTEX		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X
FERA on				at time	08:22:00	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on				at time	08:22:30	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	288.5	Cold	285.3		
Target heating						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	08:25:30	
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						X
Turn on Deimos CPU						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software				at time	08:23:05	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$			at time	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	324.2	Cold	284.9
	Deimos:	Hot	324.13	Cold	288.35
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)
	215.1	280.5	281.3	281.8	280.8

Power changeover

Headset on before start					X
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.				X
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)					X
Exit Deimos Software (x)					X
POWER CHANGEOVER					
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton				X
Restart Deimos Software					X
System running again				at time	X
				09:52:00	

Flight #	B	Date	Operator(s)	log page	2	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks	Sys			
09:40:36			CH16 worked briefly but failed after scan head re-started on ground prior to Take Off	Marss			
10:40:28		24000	Time out by 3 seconds – reset	Marss			
10:53:50	P1	24000	Profile 1 climb				
10:56:27	P1	26000	Interrupt of profile 1 climb				
10:59:30	P1	26000	Re start of profile 1 climb				
11:01:33	R1	28000	End of profile 1 climb – start of run 1				
11:15:44	R1	28000	End of run				
11:17:07	P2	28000	Start of profile 2 descent				
11:20:13	R2	26000	End of profile 2 descent – Start of run 2				
11:25:31	R2	26000	End of run				
11:28:00	P3.1	26000	Start of saw tooth through ci layer descent				
11:32:54	P3.2	21500	Ascent				
11:39:31	P3.2	28000	End of profile				
11:41:13	P4.1	28000	Start of saw tooth descent through ci layer				
11:50:15	P4.2	20000	End of 4.1 – start of 4.2 ascent				
11:55:09	P4.2	24500	End of profile 4.2 – start of run 3				
12:08:13	R3	24500	End of run				
12:09:54	P5	24500	Start of profile climb				
12:16:13	P5	30000	End of profile				
12:18:32	P6	30000	Start of profile descent				
12:20:42	P6	28000	End of profile				
12:22:44	R4	28000	Start of run				
12:33:14	R4	28000	End of run – start of profile 7 ascent				
12:35:54	P7	30000	End of profile 7 ascent				
12:37:52	R5	30000	Start of run 5				
12:38:17		30000	Dropsonde 1				
12:43:26		30000	Dropsonde 2				
12:48:55		30000	Dropsonde 3				
12:49:13	R5	30000	End of run				
13:00:00	P8	22000	End of profile descents				
13:00:23	P9	22000	Start of profile ascent				
13:03:14	P9	24000	End of profile ascent				
13:06:20	R6	24000	Start of run				
13:17:22	R6	24000	End of run				
13:19:24	P10.1	24000	Start of saw tooth ascent				
13:25:17	P10.1	30000	End of profile ascent start of profile descent				
13:30:16	P10.2	26000	End of profile descent				
13:32:20	R7	26000	Start of run				
13:39:55			Reset time as 5 seconds gained	Marss			
13:44:18	R7	26000	End of run – start of profile climb				
13:46:42	P11	28000	Interrupt of profile climb				
13:49:18	P11	28000	Re-start of profile climb				
13:51:15	P11	30000	End of profile climb – start of run				
13:59:21	R8	30000	End of run – start of profile descent				
14:06:52	P12	22000	Interrupt of profile descent				
14:08:49	P12	22000	Re-start of profile descent				
14:11:28	P12	20000	End of profile descent – start of run				
14:21:32	R9	20000	End of run. End of science.				

Flight:

B258

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turbulence Check Press:
- Turbulence Diff Press:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3010A:
- INC:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Report Created 19/01/2007 11:35:51

Last Updated:

17/01/2007 15:36:55

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B258

Date: 16th January 2007

Instruments

1. Cruciform GPS – u/s
2. TWC status flagged at high level / low temperatures (< -41 degC). Sample Temp below normal operating limits i.e. = 595 DRSU, should be above 640 DRSU. Detector signal doesn't respond to changes in humidity very well.
3. Turbulence probe P0 froze from ~ 1008Z to ??Z. Water may not be getting into the traps but remaining in the pipes. Checked ports at Newcastle. Water dripping out of lower port. Nothing in centre port trap. Water or debris may be in
4. Downward and Rear Facing cameras - looks like water inside window during taxi.
5. DEC Terminal window - being corrupted by sections of other windows even when DEC Term is on top. Rebooted pc pre-flight, still the same.
6. CVI – hasn't been connected since refitting, most cables still behind dado panel. Connected up in flight but don't know if it's fully working.
7. Upper Pyrgeometer okay till 1022 then signal dropped to – 800W/m². Recovered occasionally during flight. May be temperature related?
8. CO noisy from 11:45Z onwards. DEIMOS switched on during transit return from Newcastle, didn't appear to cause any interference on the CO.
9. Core Chem pump switches (NO & O3) bent, pack some spares for GFDEX!
10. Heimann Calibration control unit – doesn't appear to be controlling target temperature consistently.
11. DEIMOS – caused a lot of noise on PCASP during the transit test.

Aircraft

1. Water drained off cabin ceiling onto floor and Core Console fore at start of taxi.
2. Intercom box on Jif Rack intermittent in Tx mode on Training Net pre-flight.
3. Oxygen panel at Port Window 9 partly down. LTI pipe at JIF rack stopping it from coming right down.

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 16/1/07

Flight No: B28

Pre-Flighter: Doug A.

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezovorv	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input type="checkbox"/> na	FWVS	Set up	not fitted.
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	CAUSE ON : PLANNED
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	not fitted
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf ➔

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Traps empty (weekly only)		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B258:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	8 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1	15 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Correct Mission Scientist Debrief replaces previous version
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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